

PreMETS

PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training

D4.1 PreMETS platform

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Abbreviations and Terminology

Abbreviations	
PM	Predictive Maintenance

Terminology	

Executive Summary

The D4.1 is a DEC (Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.) deliverable of the PreMETS platform. The PreMETS platform successfully launched and tested. The platform is available in EN, RO, EL, IT, DE, NE, SR. A short description of the PreMETS platform is provided bellow.

1. Short Description

The PreMETS platform (<https://premets-platform.eu/>) has been successfully developed as a cloud-based solution on Microsoft Azure by CERTH team, integrating multiple services to support predictive maintenance (PM) training.

Figure 1: Platform's QR code

Key developments include:

- (i) **Platform Infrastructure & UX** – A user-friendly interface enabling seamless navigation and service integration.;
- (ii) **Bespoke Training Services** – Learning content is integrated via SCORM/MOODLE, providing structured educational resources.;
- (iii) **Ethical Learner Analytics** – A tool for tracking learning progress, preferences, and performance, allowing trainers to personalize learning paths while respecting data privacy.;
- (iv) **External Service Integration** – The SCEnAT's sustainability assessment capabilities covered by linking PM with sustainability and by offering particular modules or case studies focusing on supply chain environmental impact within PM. In addition, the Teaching Factory connects learners with industries for real-world application via Microsoft Teams video conferencing.;
- (v) **Skill Forecasting** – Identifies future PM skill demands by analysing training needs, learner feedback, and industry trends.;
- (vi) **Microcredential Certification** – Supports Europass Digital Certificates, ensuring formal recognition of acquired skills. The terms of use, the cookies policy and the privacy policy are also developed to cover EU requirements and regulations.

The PreMETS platform (figure 1) developed and reviewed by the PreMETS partners. It is available in EN, RO, EL, IT, DE, NE, SR languages. The translations delivered by PreMETS partners.